

ISic3146

I.Sicily inscription 3146

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

graffiti

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329958

1. [— — —]KACIC
2. [— — —]KOCKI
3. [— — —]TOPOC
4. [— — —] Δ AC² Δ AG (ed. pr.)².
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645487

PHI 329958

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 18.0407

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1960.0461

Agnello, S.L. 1956. Scavi recenti nelle catacombe di Vigna Cassia a Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 32: 7-27. At 25-26o

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